

From Religion to Ethnonationalism: The Argument for Civil Society-Based Programming in Bosnia and Herzegovina

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Abstract:

Civil society organisations (CSOs) are widely recognised as critical actors in preventing and countering violent extremism, yet existing scholarship has overwhelmingly focused on religious radicalisation—particularly Salafism—while neglecting right-wing ethnonationalism. This article argues that community-based prevention and de-radicalisation strategies developed in response to Salafist extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina are not only relevant but transferable to ethnonationalist radicalisation. Drawing on social identity theory and interdisciplinary literature on radicalisation, the article analyses how group belonging, identity formation, and community legitimacy function across ideological contexts. Using Bosnia as a critical case, the study synthesises existing empirical research, policy analysis, and qualitative interview material to demonstrate that civil society-led interventions—particularly those emphasising intergroup dialogue, critical thinking, and local legitimacy—address shared underlying mechanisms of radicalisation. The article contributes to debates in terrorism studies and nationalism scholarship by reframing ethnonationalism as a form of radicalisation amenable to established CVE approaches, while highlighting the indispensable role of civil society in sustaining long-term prevention and disengagement.

Key words:

Bosnia, Ethnonationalism, Radicalisation, Civil Society Organisations, Identity

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Introduction

Civil society organisations (CSOs) play a critical role in long-term prevention, disengagement, and de-radicalisation. Existing scholarship consistently demonstrates that sustained personal relationships, community embeddedness, and family support are central to successful disengagement and de-radicalisation outcomes. At the micro level, Social Identity Theory helps explain these dynamics by showing how individuals construct their sense of self through group membership, often reinforcing in-group cohesion through the exclusion or stigmatisation of perceived ‘others’ (Tajfel and Turner, 1986). These identity-based processes are central to both radicalisation and efforts to counter it.

This paper examines right-wing radicalisation and counter-radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina from a local, community-centred perspective, drawing on interpretive approaches, political anthropology, and political ethnography. It argues that community-based interventions—particularly those that cultivate critical thinking skills and facilitate intergroup dialogue—are essential to effective prevention and intervention. Building on insights from existing Salafist counter-radicalisation programming in Bosnia, the paper further argues that these methods are transferable to efforts addressing right-wing ethnonationalism.

This study departs from previous research on extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina in two key ways. First, the existing literature has disproportionately focused on foreign fighters and Salafi communities, marginalising ethnonationalism as a form of radicalisation despite its broader social and political salience. Second, the analysis demonstrates that ethnonationalist extremists across Bosniak, Serb, and Croat communities share significant commonalities in attitudes and worldviews, even when their ideologies are framed as mutually antagonistic (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). These shared characteristics point to the limitations of ethnically segmented approaches and underscore the need for comprehensive strategies that transcend ethnic divisions. The paper argues that CSOs are uniquely positioned to facilitate such approaches and concludes by outlining evidence-informed recommendations for structuring effective civil society-led programmes.

Literature Review

This literature review provides a brief overview of the radicalisation and counter-radicalisation theory most applicable for evaluating the Bosnian response to Salafism and right-wing ethnonationalism. This paper adopts a processual view of radicalisation and agrees that there is no set universal definition (Nasser-Eddine et al., 2011). While there is an identified interplay among the micro-, meso-, and macro-levels of analysis that provides a holistic view of the drivers of radicalisation, this paper focuses on the micro- and meso-levels.

The Micro-Level

Micro-level analyses centre on the individual and remain dominant within radicalisation research. At this level, radicalisation is frequently associated with experiences of alienation from the social or political status quo, which can provide psychological justification for adopting ideologies that frame that status quo as illegitimate or hostile (Keys-Turner, 2011). Schmid (2013) identifies a constellation of factors commonly associated with micro-level vulnerability,

including identity crises, marginalisation, discrimination, relative deprivation, humiliation, stigmatisation, and moral outrage, often accompanied by feelings of vicarious revenge.

Social Identity Theory offers a particularly useful framework for understanding how these individual experiences translate into group-based radicalisation. The theory posits that individuals derive a significant portion of their self-concept from group membership and that perceived status differentials between in-groups and out-groups can intensify processes of otherisation (Tajfel and Turner, 1986). In this context, radicalisation operates through the consolidation of a threatened or elevated group identity, whereby negative attributes are ascribed to out-groups in order to reinforce in-group cohesion and self-esteem. These identity dynamics underpin the mobilisation of individuals not only at the interpersonal level, but also at broader communal, national, and transnational scales.

The Meso-Level

Meso-level analyses shift attention from individual psychology to the social environments in which radicalisation is embedded. This approach emphasises the role of socio-cultural and ideological contexts in initiating and sustaining radicalisation by shaping the opportunities, narratives, and relational structures available to individuals (Keys-Turner, 2011). Central to this level is the concept of the radical milieu: a supportive or complicit social surround that normalises extremist ideas and behaviours, and provides emotional rewards such as belonging, purpose, and solidarity (Schmid, 2013).

The significance of the meso-level is particularly evident in right-wing extremism, where perceived threats to racial, ethnic, or national groups function as powerful push factors. Group-level propaganda in this context typically draws on cultural myths and identity narratives, framing violence as morally justified through processes of dehumanisation and moral disengagement (Vergani et al., 2020). Similar mechanisms are observed in studies of Islamic radicalisation, where group dynamics—including peer pressure, strong intra-group bonds, fulfilment of belonging and identity needs, and the influence of family or kinship networks—play a decisive role in sustaining extremist commitment (Vergani et al., 2020).

Online environments increasingly replicate these meso-level dynamics by providing digital spaces for community formation, narrative reinforcement, and social validation. Across ideological contexts, the literature identifies recurring demographic patterns, with extremists most frequently described as young men, and, in the case of far-right movements, predominantly white individuals born in the societies in which they radicalise (Vergani et al., 2020). These patterns underscore the importance of social context and group affiliation, rather than ideology alone, in understanding pathways into radicalisation.

Disengagement vs De-radicalisation

Disengagement and de-radicalisation both address individuals who have already been exposed to or involved in extremist ideologies or organisations, yet the literature distinguishes them as analytically and empirically distinct processes. Although the terms are sometimes used

interchangeably, this conflation obscures important differences in mechanisms and outcomes. Disengagement refers primarily to behavioural change—most notably the cessation of participation in extremist activities—whereas de-radicalisation entails a substantive transformation of beliefs and ideological commitments.

De-radicalisation is commonly defined as the process through which individuals reject extremist worldviews and adopt beliefs aligned with socially accepted or non-violent norms (Rabasa et al., 2010). It involves a fundamental shift in cognitive frameworks, such that the individual no longer adheres to the ideological foundations that previously justified extremist behaviour. By contrast, disengagement does not require ideological renunciation. Drawing on Ebaugh's (1988) concept of role exit, disengagement occurs when individuals withdraw from the roles, practices, or organisational memberships associated with extremism, even if elements of the underlying worldview remain intact. As Windisch et al. (2016) emphasise, an individual may disengage from violence or organisational activity while continuing to hold radical beliefs, making disengagement a necessary but insufficient condition for de-radicalisation.

Disengagement can occur through both voluntary and involuntary pathways and is shaped by a combination of push and pull factors as well as exit barriers. Voluntary disengagement is most commonly triggered by ideological disillusionment, leadership failures, interpersonal conflict, or personal life changes, including family considerations (Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013). These dynamics underscore the importance of preventative and early-intervention programming that identifies and addresses the conditions under which individuals begin to question their involvement. By targeting the relational and contextual factors that facilitate disengagement, such interventions can create exit pathways before ideological commitments become fully entrenched, thereby increasing the prospects for longer-term de-radicalisation.

Push and Pull Factors

The literature on ethnonationalist extremism closely parallels research on Islamic extremism and other forms of radical group membership, emphasising that radicalisation does not stem from a single causal driver. Instead, scholars identify recurring patterns involving grievances, unmet social and psychological needs, ideational framing, group dynamics, and the normalisation of violence. As Neumann (2017) argues, radicalisation across ideological contexts emerges from societal tensions and fault lines that generate identity conflicts and perceptions of injustice, marginalisation, and exclusion.

A central mechanism in this process is the fulfilment of emotional and social needs through group membership. Extremist organisations offer belonging, community, purpose, and recognition—often framed in terms of adventure, power, or moral significance—which can be particularly appealing to individuals experiencing social or economic insecurity (Neumann, 2017). These affective incentives are reinforced through ideational narratives that identify a vilified 'other' and present the group's ideology as a coherent solution to perceived grievances. Radicalisation thus operates as a social process, sustained by interpersonal ties and reinforced by authority figures, charismatic leaders, or tightly knit peer networks that generate trust, loyalty, and peer pressure (Neumann, 2017).

Empirical studies further highlight the structural conditions that function as push factors into ethnonationalist extremism. Vergani et al. (2020) identify relative deprivation—variously expressed as inequality, exclusion, frustration, victimisation, or stigmatisation—as one of the most consistent predictors of radicalisation. In the Bosnian context, Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that individuals with lower levels of education or dissatisfaction with income, family life, and future prospects are significantly more likely to legitimise violence. Their analysis also reveals a strong association between permanent employment and affiliation with ruling ethnonationalist parties, indicating how political patronage networks can reinforce far-right mobilisation rather than mitigate it.

These dynamics underscore the importance of civil society interventions that address radicalisation as a socially embedded and relational process rather than solely an ideological one. CSOs are uniquely positioned to intervene at the level of grievances, identity, and belonging by providing alternative forms of community, recognition, and participation that do not rely on exclusionary or violent narratives. By engaging individuals before extremist identities become fully consolidated—and by addressing the socio-economic and relational contexts in which grievances are interpreted—civil society actors can disrupt recruitment pathways and reduce the appeal of ethnonationalist mobilisation.

The Role of Civil Society

Extremism manifests across the political spectrum, and effective prevention and counter-radicalisation strategies must therefore avoid privileging or excluding particular ideological forms. A consistent finding in the literature is that counter-extremism programming must be grounded in the protection of human rights and civil liberties, including freedoms of expression, religion, and association, and must avoid stigmatising specific communities. Where restrictions on these freedoms are deemed necessary, they must be legally justified, legitimate, and proportionate to the threat identified (OSCE, 2018). This rights-based framework is central to maintaining the legitimacy and effectiveness of counter-extremism interventions.

Within this context, civil society organisations play a critical and distinctive role. The OSCE defines civil society as a diverse constellation of formal and informal actors engaged in public life to advance shared values and social objectives (OSCE, 2018). These actors—including youth groups, women’s organisations, religious leaders, educators, and community representatives—are uniquely positioned to deliver prevention and intervention initiatives because of their credibility, social embeddedness, and sustained engagement with local populations. Civil society actors are often better equipped than state institutions to identify community-specific grievances and vulnerabilities that increase susceptibility to extremist narratives, particularly among marginalised or at-risk groups (OSCE, 2018).

The OSCE’s prevention–intervention–rehabilitation framework further clarifies the functional space in which civil society operates. Prevention efforts focus on strengthening community resilience through awareness-raising, education, dialogue initiatives, and trust-building activities, including interfaith engagement and collaboration with local institutions (OSCE, 2018; Neumann, 2017). Intervention strategies target individuals already exhibiting at-risk behaviours, often through voluntary disengagement and exit pathways designed to prevent escalation into

violence. Rehabilitation programmes, typically operating in custodial or post-custodial settings, aim to support longer-term disengagement and de-radicalisation (OSCE, 2018; Neumann, 2017). While rehabilitation frequently involves state institutions, civil society actors remain essential in providing continuity of support during reintegration and aftercare.

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, civil society has been particularly central to prevention and early-intervention efforts. Existing programmes emphasise community-based approaches that combine critical thinking skills, interfaith dialogue, and locally grounded engagement as core elements of resilience-building (Welty, 2022). The OSCE (2018) further highlights the importance of involving youth, families, women, victims of terrorism, and religious, cultural, and educational leaders in counter-extremism initiatives, recognising their capacity to foster social cohesion and challenge exclusionary narratives from within communities. By operating within a rights-based framework and leveraging local legitimacy, civil society organisations play an indispensable role in sustaining long-term prevention, disengagement, and de-radicalisation processes.

CSOs and Religious Radicalism

Insights from fieldwork interviews further illustrate how identity dynamics and community support shape disengagement and de-radicalisation processes. In an interview, Amra Pandžo (2019) reflected on her experience as a former Salafi and the lessons drawn from her disengagement that now inform her work as a civil society practitioner. Her account demonstrates a core insight of Social Identity Theory: radicalisation and exit are shaped by tensions between competing group memberships. Pandžo described how perceived incompatibilities between her Salafi identity, cultural background, and gendered expectations generated ideological disillusionment and ultimately facilitated disengagement.

While Pandžo could not clearly identify the motivations that initially led her to join a Salafi community, she consistently emphasised several factors that supported her disengagement and longer-term de-radicalisation. These included dissatisfaction with doctrinal positions—particularly regarding the role of women—conflicts with her cultural identity, sustained support from family and neighbourhood networks, the development of critical thinking skills, and access to religious education that encouraged interpretive plurality. Importantly, she underscored the value of community-based approaches that integrate interfaith dialogue and critical reflection, principles she now applies in her peacebuilding and civil society work (Welty, 2022).

These insights align closely with the broader disengagement and de-radicalisation literature, which identifies community, belonging, and education as central mechanisms in both recruitment and exit processes (Ebaugh, 1988; Rabasa et al., 2010; Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013; Windisch et al., 2016). Extremist groups often exploit unmet needs for belonging and purpose during recruitment; paradoxically, these same needs must be addressed to facilitate successful exit. In Pandžo's case, the presence of a supportive social environment reduced the perceived risks of leaving and mitigated fears associated with social isolation. As Dalgaard-Nielsen (2013) notes, disengagement is frequently triggered by burnout, moral doubt, or changing personal

priorities, but without supportive networks, individuals may delay exit or relapse due to fear of losing their only source of community.

The literature further emphasises that disengagement alone is insufficient without opportunities for identity reconstruction and reintegration. Rabasa et al. (2010) argue that individuals exiting extremist movements must develop alternative identities and social networks to reduce the risk of recidivism. In Bosnia, however, communal cleavages—particularly between mainstream Muslim communities and Salafi groups—can create significant reintegration barriers, reinforcing hesitation to disengage and limiting pathways out of extremism. For exit to be viable, individuals must perceive movement between social groups as possible and socially legitimate.

These dynamics have direct implications for civil society-led counter-radicalisation. The mechanisms that facilitate recruitment—identity affirmation, community formation, and education—can be strategically repurposed in prevention and disengagement programming, including in efforts targeting right-wing ethnonationalism. Strengthening community resilience through education and critical engagement is central to countering extremist ideology and empowering local leaders to challenge exclusionary narratives (Neumann, 2011). In Bosnia, initiatives such as the Nahla Centre for Education and Research, Mali Koraci (Small Steps), Resonant Voices Initiative, Inicijativa Etos, and Youth Education exemplify this approach by prioritising skills development, community building, interfaith dialogue, and digital literacy. Many of these programmes deliberately engage youth and women, recognising their influence within families and communities. Despite demonstrated successes, their broader impact remains constrained by the fact that religious radicalisation is often perceived as less urgent than ethnonationalist extremism within Bosnian society, shaping funding priorities and public engagement (Welty, 2022).

Challenges in the Bosnian Context

Civil society-led de-radicalisation programmes in Bosnia and Herzegovina face persistent constraints related to institutional capacity, funding, and issue prioritisation. Interview data indicate that effective civil society interventions rely on community-oriented approaches that directly engage individuals at risk, with particular emphasis on interfaith dialogue, critical thinking skills, and organisational capacity development. However, a significant challenge lies in the relatively low salience of Salafist radicalisation within broader public perceptions. As Welty (2022) notes, most Bosnians do not view religious radicalisation as an issue that meaningfully affects everyday life. As Funk (2019) explains, Salafism is not widely denied as a phenomenon, but it is rarely considered socially urgent.

By contrast, ethnonationalism occupies a far more prominent place in public concern. Practitioners interviewed for this study consistently framed nationalism—not Salafism—as the primary radicalising force in Bosnia. Funk (2019) captures this shift succinctly, arguing that “the key radicals in Bosnia are not Salafists, but nationalists, nationalist rhetoric, the nationalist element.” This reframing reflects a broader tension between local threat perceptions and donor-driven programming priorities. Salafist radicalisation emerged as a focal point largely because it attracted international attention and funding as a “new” security concern, rather than

because it aligned with locally perceived drivers of instability (Funk, 2019). This disconnect reinforces the central argument of this paper: lessons learned from Salafist counter-radicalisation must be redirected toward addressing ethnonationalist extremism, where local relevance and social resonance are far greater.

Capacity limitations further constrain civil society effectiveness. Interviews with social workers and representatives of Centres for Social Work confirm that public welfare institutions lack the resources and training necessary to meet the needs of vulnerable populations, including those at risk of radicalisation (Turčalo and Veljan, 2018). Professionals consistently reported that insufficient institutional capacity and inadequate training undermine trust between service providers and the very individuals most in need of support. These structural weaknesses are compounded by the limited reach of community-level programming. Much existing Preventing and Countering Violent Extremism (P/CVE) activity remains initiated and directed at the state or entity level, making it difficult to assess responsiveness to local conditions or measure long-term impact (Turčalo and Veljan, 2018).

The absence of genuinely locally owned and community-specific P/CVE initiatives poses a significant obstacle to effective prevention and intervention. Turčalo and Veljan (2018) warn that the lack of locally grounded programming risks undermining social trust and reducing community engagement, particularly in contexts shaped by distinct historical and cultural experiences. These concerns are reinforced by Azinović and Jusić (2016), who identify persistent flaws in Bosnian CVE programming, including reliance on assumed rather than empirically grounded drivers of radicalisation, insufficient contextualisation, and limited inclusion of local expertise. Such shortcomings not only reduce programme effectiveness but may also produce unintended harms by misidentifying target groups, marginalising local actors, and reinforcing perceptions of external imposition in domestic security affairs.

Ethnic Conflict and Narratives of Identity

Ethnic conflict may manifest in both violent and non-violent forms and is best understood as a socially constructed process rather than an inevitable outcome of cultural difference. Wolff (2013) defines ethnic conflict as group conflict interpreted and organised along real or perceived ethnonational divides, in which at least one party mobilises around a distinct ethnonational identity. Ethnonationalism, in this sense, is sustained through adversity and perceived denial, as concessions or institutional recognition can reinforce rather than dissolve separate identities by providing new rallying points for mobilisation (Connor, 1973).

Scholarship on situational ethnicity further highlights the contextual and relational nature of ethnic identity. Nagata (1974) and Mitchell (1974) argue that ethnicity is not fixed but emerges through social interaction, shaped by circumstances, perceptions, and political environments. In multiethnic states, ethnic identification draws on place of birth, lineage, tradition, and culture, but its salience fluctuates depending on context (Zdeb, 2019). Bosnia and Herzegovina exemplifies this dynamic particularly clearly. Historically and contemporarily, ethnicity has functioned less as a static marker of belonging than as a strategic and situational resource shaping social relations, state institutions, and political competition (Zdeb, 2019). As Connor (1973) notes, ethnic groups become nations only when members themselves internalise a

shared sense of distinctiveness, underscoring the importance of self-definition in ethnonational mobilisation.

Despite Bosnia's post-war reputation as a deeply divided society, historical accounts emphasise long-standing patterns of coexistence and everyday pluralism. Fine argues that tolerance characterised much of Bosnia's history, with conflict emerging primarily through external or elite-driven mobilisation (cited in Toal and Dahlman, 2011). Andjelić (2003) similarly observes that coexistence and mutual accommodation outweighed open hostility for much of Bosnia's past. Cultural historians describe this pattern as a "unity in diversity," in which difference was both recognised and normalised within everyday social life (Lovrenović, 1999). Anthropological studies further demonstrate that exposure to cultural and religious diversity was embedded in identity formation for most Bosnians, producing ambivalent but enduring traditions of coexistence (Bringa, 1993).

These traditions were institutionalised through social practices such as *komšijski odnosi* (neighbourly relations) and *zajednički život* (common life), which emphasised accommodation rather than assimilation (Zdeb, 2019). Even contemporary identity categories—such as "Bosnian Muslim"—often denote cultural and historical belonging rather than strict religious adherence, reflecting a lived identity shaped by secularisation, folk traditions, and shared experience (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). Notably, research suggests that among individuals holding extreme ethnonationalist views, shared attitudes and behavioural patterns often outweigh differences across Bosniak, Serb, and Croat communities, despite divergent symbolic expressions of tradition (Halilović and Veljan, 2021).

Ethnic consciousness nevertheless relies on the recognition of difference, constructing a referent "other" against which group identity is defined (Connor, 1972). Narratives play a central role in this process by shaping meaning, legitimising political claims, and delineating moral boundaries between "us" and "them" (Demirel, 2023). In post-conflict societies, narratives of past suffering are particularly potent, as they reinforce collective identity by defining victimhood, blame, and moral responsibility. Such narratives can impede reconciliation when they harden in-group and out-group distinctions or compete over exclusive claims to victimhood (Demirel, 2023).

In Bosnia, the uneven distribution of wartime violence has intensified these dynamics. Differential exposure to violence has shaped divergent understandings of responsibility and justice, complicating efforts to construct inclusive post-war narratives (Demirel, 2021). As a result, reconciliation is often conceptualised along ethnic lines, with different communities advancing incompatible expectations. While Bosniaks tend to support a moral remembrance model aligned with international norms, many Bosnian Serbs frame reconciliation as the rejection of narratives that cast them as collective aggressors (Demirel, 2023). These tensions are reinforced through denial, historical revisionism, and the mobilisation of wartime symbols and slurs, which continue to function as markers of exclusion and hostility in public discourse (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021).

These narrative dynamics have direct implications for radicalisation. As Oruc and Obradovic (2020) argue, future research must more closely examine the relationship between radicalisation and perceptions of wartime outcomes, justice, and what constitutes a "just peace." In Bosnia

and Herzegovina, ethnonationalist radicalisation is deeply embedded in contested histories and narrative competition, underscoring the need for interventions that address identity, memory, and meaning-making alongside material grievances.

The Relationship Between Religious Extremism and Ethnonationalism

Salafist radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina culminated in two waves of Bosnian-born foreign fighters travelling to Syria and Iraq between 2012 and 2016. Estimates suggest that approximately 220–330 Bosnians participated in the conflict, making Bosnia the largest contributor of foreign fighters in the Western Balkans and the second-highest per capita contributor in Europe (Counter Extremism Project, 2021). By 2016, these flows had largely ceased, and many Salafist parajamaats were dismantled (Azinović and Jusić, 2016). This period prompted heightened international attention to Islamic extremism in Bosnia. At the same time, however, ethnonationalism and political extremism were intensifying domestically. Interview data indicate that many Bosnians viewed religious radicalisation as less pressing than nationalist rhetoric and mobilisation. As Funk (2019) observed, practitioners increasingly framed nationalism itself as a form of radicalisation, arguing that “the key radicals in Bosnia are not Salafists, but nationalists.” Reflecting this shift, scholars and policymakers have begun to acknowledge ethnonationalism as a central security and social challenge alongside religious extremism (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021).

Although Salafism and ethnonationalism are often treated as analytically distinct, the literature highlights significant points of convergence. Perry (2017) argues that both occupy a similar position on the rightward ideological spectrum, particularly in their repatriarchal logics and use of gender norms. Each represents a cultural backlash against feminist gains and promotes an idealised, moralised vision of a “better imagined past.” Both forms of extremism rely on exclusionary identity construction, defining a hostile ‘other’ against which in-group identity is affirmed and sustained. These dynamics are closely tied to nationalism and ethnic politics, privileging notions of blood, heritage, and immutable belonging over civic or pluralist conceptions of community (Perry, 2017).

Empirical research further underscores the entanglement of religion and ethnonationalism in Bosnia. Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that religion plays a significant role in everyday life for the vast majority of respondents, with a substantial proportion reporting strong adherence to religious teachings. Crucially, higher levels of religious devotion correlate with greater acceptance of violence when framed as defence or revenge on behalf of one’s ethnic or religious group. The authors argue that radical interpretations of religion can reinforce ethnonationalist narratives, intensifying polarisation and legitimising extremist attitudes.

Beyond belief systems, religious symbolism functions as a powerful narrative resource within ethnonationalist mobilisation. During the Bosnian war, religiously inflected stereotypes—such as Croats as Ustaše, Serbs as Chetniks, and Muslims as *Balija* or “Turks”—were widely deployed to inflame nationalist sentiment (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). Religious identity also became a key mechanism of wartime mobilisation: for Bosnian Muslims,

persecution intensified religious identification, while for Catholic and Orthodox Christians, religion was invoked as justification for what was framed as a struggle for cultural and national survival (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). Christianity, in particular, was frequently positioned as a superior civilisational principle opposed to Islam, which was portrayed as foreign or invasive.

In the contemporary Bosnian context, extremism and hate speech are most commonly associated with right-wing movements overlapping with Serb and Croat ethnonationalism, often infused with Christian symbolism, alongside radical forms of Islam and Bosniak or Bosnian nationalism (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). While Orthodox and Catholic practices are not typically categorised as extremist, they assume radical significance when mobilised in exclusionary or ethnonationalist ways. Social media analysis reveals the extent to which religious imagery and clerical authority are incorporated into right-wing ethnonationalist discourse, with groups prominently displaying religious symbols and highlighting ties to religious institutions and leaders (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). These online performances frequently intersect with misogynistic, chauvinistic, and antisemitic narratives, targeting perceived out-groups through stereotyping, essentialisation, and abuse (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021).

Taken together, this literature demonstrates that Salafism and ethnonationalism in Bosnia are not isolated phenomena but overlapping forms of identity-based extremism. Their shared reliance on moralised narratives, gendered hierarchies, and religious symbolism helps explain why strategies developed to counter Salafist radicalisation may be adapted to address ethnonationalist extremism more effectively.

Key Recommended Elements for Programming

Inter-group Dialogue

Building on the demonstrated effectiveness of interfaith initiatives in countering religious extremism, civil society organisations (CSOs) should prioritise sustained inter-group dialogue as a core strategy for addressing ethnonationalist radicalisation (Welty, 2022). Empirical evidence from Bosnia indicates that meaningful contact across ethnic lines is associated with lower support for violence, even among individuals who hold ethnonationalist attitudes. Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that respondents who regularly interacted with members of other ethnic groups were more receptive to reconciliation, more likely to recognise the harms of glorifying war criminals, and less resistant to social and civic integration across ethnic boundaries. These patterns highlight the capacity of inter-group engagement to weaken exclusionary narratives and reduce the legitimisation of violence.

CSOs are uniquely positioned to facilitate such dialogue because of their local credibility, sustained community presence, and ability to convene participants across social and institutional divides. Through structured dialogue, joint community initiatives, and educational programming, CSOs can create environments in which contested identities and historical grievances can be addressed without securitisation or stigmatisation. Given the documented

overlap between religious and political extremism in Bosnia, these efforts should explicitly include engagement with religious communities. Educational and awareness-raising initiatives that address the instrumentalisation of religion by far-right movements not only strengthen broader societal resilience but also protect religious communities from co-optation by exclusionary ideologies. Collaboration with the Interreligious Council is therefore essential to ensure legitimacy, inclusivity, and sustained impact in CSO-led interventions (Halilović and Veljan, 2021).

The Role of Women

Women play a critical yet frequently underutilised role in countering radicalisation and extremism, particularly within the Bosnian context. Empirical evidence suggests that women are generally less supportive of violent extremism, and that attitudes toward gender equality are strongly associated with views on violence. Halilović and Veljan (2021) identify a direct relationship between the rejection of gender equality and increased support for violence, indicating that patriarchal value systems function as a risk factor for radicalisation.

Despite this, women's public engagement and activism in Bosnia have often been marginalised or framed as inappropriate under dominant ethnonationalist and patriarchal ideologies (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). This marginalisation stands in tension with women's demonstrated importance in fostering family stability, community cohesion, and informal social regulation—factors consistently identified as protective against radicalisation. Civil society organisations are therefore essential in creating legitimate and accessible spaces for women's participation in prevention and intervention efforts. By supporting women's leadership, amplifying their voices, and integrating gender-sensitive approaches into programming, CSOs can counter exclusionary narratives while strengthening community-level resilience to extremism.

The Role of Youth

Youth represent a key demographic in both the prevention of radicalisation and the reproduction of extremist narratives. Research consistently shows that young men are more susceptible to risk-taking behaviour and violent mobilisation (Budd et al., 2005; Farrington, 2003; Silke, 2008). In Bosnia and Herzegovina, these vulnerabilities are exacerbated by persistently high youth unemployment, social exclusion, and limited future prospects (CIJA, 2016; Bećirević, 2018). Oruc and Obradovic (2020) argue that these conditions foster grievance and a desire for revenge, placing young people at heightened risk of radicalisation relative to other age groups.

Empirical studies further indicate that support for violent extremism is more pronounced among younger cohorts. Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that respondents aged 18–35 express higher levels of acceptance of violence, while earlier qualitative research suggests that youth who did not experience the ethnically heterogeneous society of Yugoslavia are more likely to adopt ethnonationalist attitudes (Hvidemose, 2010). Notably, even adolescents too young to remember the war actively reproduce ethnonationalist symbols and narratives, indicating the

persistence of intergenerational transmission of identity-based grievances. Comparative evidence suggests little change in these patterns between 2010 and 2021, underscoring the durability of youth vulnerability to extremist messaging.

Digital environments further intensify these risks. Studies show that online media play a significant role in shaping radical views among young people, amplifying exclusionary narratives and facilitating exposure to extremist content (Suraya and Mulyana, 2020). Combined with economic frustration and social marginalisation, these dynamics increase susceptibility to push and pull factors associated with ethnonationalist mobilisation. Hvidemose (2010) reports widespread concern among practitioners that youth increasingly reproduce ethnic divisions and nationalist discourse, particularly as unemployment and social frustration disproportionately affect younger generations.

Civil society organisations are therefore central to youth-focused prevention efforts. CSOs are uniquely positioned to provide alternative spaces for belonging, civic engagement, and critical reflection that counteract both offline and online radicalisation pathways. Family influence remains a decisive factor in shaping youth attitudes, with household environments identified as the strongest contributor to susceptibility to ethnonationalism and radicalisation (Hvidemose, 2010). By working with families, schools, and local communities, CSOs can address these dynamics holistically—combining digital literacy, critical thinking, and inclusive identity formation to reduce the appeal of extremist narratives among young people.

Digital Literacy, Propaganda, and the Media

As with Salafist recruitment, online spaces are central to the dissemination of ethnonationalist narratives and the mobilisation of supporters (Perry, 2021). Digital platforms facilitate incremental radicalisation through self-reinforcing content dynamics, in which users are exposed to increasingly extreme material as a result of networked and algorithmic amplification (Madryha et al., 2022). These processes extend beyond explicitly extremist spaces and intersect with broader media ecosystems.

Traditional media also plays a significant role in shaping ethnonationalist discourse. Hvidemose (2010) documents how politically influenced and selectively framed reporting has contributed to the reproduction of ethnic divisions in Bosnia, with inter-ethnic incidents often exaggerated to sustain fear while examples of cooperation and coexistence receive limited attention. Such media practices reinforce polarising narratives and normalise exclusionary interpretations of social conflict.

Civil society organisations are therefore critical actors in contesting dominant narratives across both digital and traditional media. By partnering with independent media outlets, CSOs can foster public discussion around far-right discourse and expose the mechanisms through which ethnonationalist narratives are constructed and circulated (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). Civil society also plays a central role in generating and amplifying alternative narratives that foreground historical periods of coexistence and shared social experience, challenging revisionist accounts that underpin extremist mobilisation (Williams, 2019).

Effective intervention further requires accessible and credible communication strategies to counter disinformation, conspiracy theories, and hate speech. CSOs are uniquely positioned to translate complex historical and political issues into clear, locally resonant messages that strengthen public resilience to manipulation and reduce the appeal of exclusionary narratives (Halilović and Veljan, 2021).

Legal Reform

Bosnia and Herzegovina was the first state in the Western Balkans to criminalise participation in paramilitary and para-police formations through Article 162b of the Criminal Code (Official Gazette No. 47/14). While this represents an important legal precedent, existing frameworks require further expansion to address contemporary forms of right-wing extremism. Civil society organisations play a critical role in advancing this agenda by monitoring implementation gaps, documenting emerging extremist practices, and advocating for the consistent prosecution of hate speech and incitement to violence in cooperation with the police and judiciary (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). As comparative research suggests, adaptive and innovative legal instruments are essential to counter evolving extremist mobilisation strategies (Burchett et al., 2022).

Legal reform should extend beyond paramilitary activity to encompass right-wing extremist organisations more broadly, including those that mobilise through ideological programmes, public messaging, and non-violent but exclusionary activities that contribute to radicalisation and social polarisation (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). In this context, CSOs are particularly well positioned to provide evidence-based assessments of how extremist actors operate below the threshold of overt violence, ensuring that legislation remains responsive without undermining civil liberties.

These reforms must be embedded within a comprehensive strategic framework. The Strategy of Bosnia and Herzegovina for the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism (2021–2026) acknowledges the persistent threat posed by ethnic and national extremism and recognises its destabilising impact on both domestic and regional security, including its frequent entanglement with religious narratives. Aligning legal reform with updated counterterrorism strategies that explicitly address political, ethnonationalist, and religious radicalisation is therefore essential (European Commission, 2022). Importantly, the Strategy recognises civil society as a key actor in combating extremism and fostering social resilience. This acknowledgement underscores the need to move beyond state-centric approaches by institutionalising CSO participation in prevention, monitoring, and resilience-building efforts alongside legal enforcement mechanisms.

Recommendations

Drawing on the literature and the empirical findings of this study, the following recommendations outline how civil society organisations (CSOs) can more effectively address ethnonationalist radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina by adapting lessons from Salafist counter-radicalisation efforts. Taken together, these recommendations emphasise CSOs'

distinctive capacity to intervene at the level of identity, community, and narrative—areas where state-led approaches are often least effective.

First, CSOs should prioritise sustained inter-group dialogue as a core mechanism for countering ethnonationalism. Evidence from Bosnia demonstrates that regular, meaningful contact across ethnic lines reduces support for violence, increases openness to reconciliation, and weakens exclusionary narratives, even among individuals who hold ethnonationalist views. By convening Bosniaks, Croats, and Serbs in structured dialogue and joint community initiatives, CSOs can address grievances and historical narratives without securitisation or ethnic segmentation.

Second, CSOs should actively engage religious communities in education and awareness-raising initiatives that address the instrumentalisation of religion by far-right and ethnonationalist actors. Given the documented overlap between religious and political extremism in Bosnia, partnerships with religious leaders and institutions—particularly through mechanisms such as the Interreligious Council—are essential for challenging exclusionary narratives while preserving religious freedom and community trust. Such engagement also protects religious communities from co-optation by extremist movements.

Third, women should be systematically integrated into prevention and intervention efforts, not merely as beneficiaries but as leaders and programme designers. The evidence presented in this paper demonstrates a strong relationship between patriarchal value systems and support for violence, alongside women's comparatively lower endorsement of extremist positions. CSOs are therefore well positioned to counter repatriarchalisation by promoting gender equality, supporting women's leadership, and leveraging women's roles in family and community cohesion as protective factors against radicalisation.

Fourth, CSOs should prioritise youth-focused programming that addresses both structural vulnerabilities and identity-based drivers of radicalisation. High unemployment, social exclusion, and intergenerational transmission of ethnonationalist narratives place young people at particular risk. Effective CSO interventions should combine civic engagement, critical thinking, and alternative forms of belonging, while also engaging families and schools to address the broader social environments in which youth attitudes are formed.

Fifth, CSOs should expand digital literacy and media engagement initiatives to counter online radicalisation and narrative amplification. Given the central role of digital spaces in spreading ethnonationalist discourse, CSOs should partner with independent media to promote alternative narratives, challenge historical revisionism, and provide accessible responses to disinformation and conspiracy theories. Digital literacy programming should be tailored to different age groups, with particular emphasis on youth, while remaining embedded in broader community-based interventions.

Sixth, CSOs should play an active role in advancing and monitoring legal reforms related to extremism. This includes advocating for the consistent prosecution of hate speech and incitement to violence, as well as contributing evidence and expertise to the development of legislation addressing right-wing extremist organisations. Collaboration with law enforcement and judicial institutions is essential, but CSOs also function as watchdogs, ensuring that legal measures remain proportionate, rights-based, and responsive to evolving extremist practices.

Finally, CSOs should be formally integrated into the development and implementation of national and regional strategies addressing radicalisation. As Bosnia and Herzegovina's counterterrorism framework increasingly recognises ethnonationalist extremism as a persistent threat, CSO participation is crucial for grounding strategy in local realities. Institutionalised collaboration between CSOs and relevant authorities can help ensure that prevention and resilience-building efforts address political, ethnonationalist, and religious radicalisation in a coherent and context-sensitive manner.

Taken together, these recommendations underscore the central argument of this paper: that civil society is not peripheral to countering ethnonationalism in Bosnia and Herzegovina, but essential to its long-term prevention. By adapting proven community-based approaches developed in response to Salafist radicalisation, CSOs can more effectively address the identity-based, relational, and narrative dimensions of ethnonationalist extremism, contributing to greater social cohesion and regional stability.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that warrant acknowledgement. First, much of the existing literature on radicalisation and counter-radicalisation continues to prioritise violent extremism, democratic destabilisation, and terrorism, with a particular empirical emphasis on Salafism. As a result, the conceptual tools and empirical benchmarks used in this paper are more developed for religious extremism than for ethnonationalism. While this imbalance motivates the paper's core contribution—extending insights from Salafist counter-radicalisation to ethnonationalist contexts—it also constrains the analytical depth with which ethnonationalism can be theorised as a distinct form of radicalisation.

Second, the focus on Bosnia and Herzegovina necessarily limits the generalisability of the findings. Bosnia's post-conflict setting, ethnically segmented political institutions, and distinctive history of coexistence and violence shape both radicalisation pathways and the role of civil society in ways that may not translate directly to other regional or political contexts. While Bosnia provides a critical case for examining the interaction between religious and ethnonationalist extremism, caution is required when applying these findings to other societies with different historical trajectories, institutional arrangements, or patterns of identity mobilisation.

Third, while the paper identifies a set of civil society-led practices that appear effective in addressing ethnonationalist radicalisation, it does not fully explore the practical and political constraints associated with their implementation. Factors such as uneven institutional capacity, donor dependence, political resistance, and community mistrust may significantly shape the feasibility and sustainability of these interventions. Future research would benefit from more systematic evaluation of implementation challenges, including comparative assessments of why certain programmes succeed or fail in specific local settings.

Fourth, the analysis does not comprehensively account for external influences on radicalisation and prevention efforts in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Geopolitical dynamics, international interventions, transnational funding streams, and regional political developments may all shape

local radicalisation processes and civil society responses in ways that exceed the scope of this study. A fuller understanding of how domestic and international factors interact would strengthen analysis of prevention and de-radicalisation in post-conflict contexts.

More broadly, this study is situated within an ongoing scholarly debate regarding the drivers and processes of radicalisation. Despite extensive research, there remains no consensus on the relative weight of ideological, structural, relational, and individual factors in explaining why individuals engage in violent extremism or affiliate with extremist organisations. As Vergani et al. (2020) note, future research should further disentangle the interaction between push, pull, and personal factors across both cognitive and behavioural dimensions of radicalisation, with closer attention to how these dynamics vary across local contexts.

Finally, this paper treats civil society primarily as a preventive and resilience-building force, but this framing carries its own limitations. Civil society is not inherently liberal or pro-democratic and may itself become a vehicle for ethnonationalism, populism, or exclusionary politics. As Cossà et al. (2021) caution, civil society actors can propagate radical and xenophobic narratives when embedded in polarised political environments. Recognising this ambivalence is essential for avoiding overly normative assumptions about the role of civil society and for developing more nuanced approaches to engaging CSOs in counter-radicalisation efforts.

Conclusion

This article has examined the dynamics of radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina by integrating insights from radicalisation scholarship with interpretive frameworks, political anthropology, and political ethnography. By foregrounding local perspectives on right-wing ethnonationalist radicalisation, the analysis demonstrates that radicalisation is best understood as a context-dependent process shaped by the interaction of push, pull, and personal factors operating at both cognitive and behavioural levels. Attending to these interactions is essential for designing prevention and de-radicalisation strategies that are socially legitimate, locally resonant, and sustainable.

The central contribution of this study is to demonstrate the indispensable role of civil society organisations in long-term prevention, disengagement, and de-radicalisation. The findings show that personal relationships, community embeddedness, and locally grounded engagement are not ancillary to counter-radicalisation efforts but constitute their core mechanisms. Civil society actors are uniquely positioned to address identity formation, belonging, and narrative construction—key drivers of radicalisation that cannot be effectively managed through securitised or state-centric approaches alone.

Crucially, this paper argues that counter-radicalisation strategies developed in response to Salafist extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina are transferable to efforts addressing right-wing ethnonationalism. This transferability does not rest on ideological equivalence, but on shared underlying mechanisms of radicalisation, including exclusionary identity construction, grievance mobilisation, and the social reinforcement of “us versus them” narratives. As such, the study challenges the tendency to compartmentalise counter-radicalisation by ideology and instead advances a more integrated, mechanism-focused approach.

The analysis underscores the value of community-based solutions that operate across ideological divides. Inter-group and interfaith dialogue, the cultivation of critical thinking skills, and sustained investment in civil society capacity emerge as indispensable components of effective prevention and de-radicalisation programming. These approaches are particularly salient in post-conflict contexts such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, where ethnonationalist narratives remain deeply embedded in social and political life and continue to shape patterns of mobilisation.

The next stage of this research will extend these findings through an in-depth qualitative and quantitative examination of civil society organisations engaged with issues of ethnonationalism. By analysing their objectives, practices, and constraints, future research will assess the extent to which existing initiatives align with the evidence-based recommendations developed in this study and identify conditions that enable or hinder effective civil society intervention.

This article contributes to terrorism and radicalisation scholarship by reframing ethnonationalism as a form of radicalisation that is amenable to established counter-radicalisation approaches and by positioning civil society as a central pillar of prevention and social resilience. By demonstrating the adaptability of community-based strategies across ideological contexts, the study offers both a conceptual and practical framework for addressing ethnonationalist extremism in Bosnia and beyond.

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